

AN OVERVIEW OF MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN UZBEKISTAN

Ulugbek Inamov

Student of Namangan State University

Mahbuba Holmatova

Supervisor:

Teacher of Namangan State University

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Abstract: This article provides an overview of the modern methods employed in teaching English in Uzbekistan, focusing on recent educational reforms, innovative teaching practices, and ongoing challenges. It highlights the role of government initiatives, modern methodologies such as Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), and as well as CLIL. The study emphasizes the importance of continued investment in teacher training and infrastructure to ensure sustainable progress in English language education.

Key Words: English language teaching, Uzbekistan, modern methods, educational reforms, teacher training, digital learning

Introduction

In recent years, Uzbekistan has witnessed significant reforms in its education system, with a particular focus on enhancing the quality of English language teaching. The increasing importance of English as a global language has led the government to prioritize its teaching at all levels of education. Modern methodologies have been introduced to address the challenges of traditional teaching practices and align with global standards. The Presidential Decree No. PP-1875 (2012) marked a turning point in Uzbekistan's approach to English language education. The decree emphasized the need for a modern curriculum, updated teaching materials, and professional development programs for English language teachers. Additionally, partnerships with international organizations, such as the British Council and the Embassy of United States, have played a crucial role in introducing innovative teaching practices.

Modern Teaching Methods

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) CLT focuses on developing learners' speaking and listening skills through interactive activities, group discussions, and real-life simulations. Teachers are encouraged to create student-centered lessons where learners actively participate in communicative tasks. The core principle of CLT is that language is best learned through

authentic communication rather than rote memorization of grammar rules. Lessons often include role-playing, problem-solving tasks, and collaborative dialogues that mimic real-world situations. For example, students might simulate ordering food at a restaurant or engaging in a job interview, providing a practical context for language use. Moreover, error correction in CLT is often handled in a way that encourages learners rather than discourages them, focusing on fluency over immediate grammatical accuracy. Teachers act as facilitators, guiding students in conversations and ensuring that every learner gets the opportunity to participate. The method also encourages peer-to-peer interaction, which helps students build confidence in their speaking abilities.

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) emphasizes completing meaningful tasks as a way to acquire language skills. Students engage in problem-solving activities, role-plays, and collaborative projects that require the use of English in authentic contexts. Unlike traditional grammar-focused methods, TBLT prioritizes practical usage of the target language. Tasks in TBLT are often designed to reflect real-world situations, such as planning a trip, writing an email, or creating a group presentation. These activities not only promote language practice but also develop critical thinking, teamwork, and problem-solving skills. TBLT lessons typically follow a three-stage structure: pre-task, task cycle, and post-task. In the pre-task phase, the teacher introduces the topic, provides relevant vocabulary, and sets the context. During the task cycle, students work in pairs or groups to complete the assigned task while the teacher monitors and offers support. In the post-task phase, learners reflect on their performance, share their results with the class, and receive constructive feedback. This reflective stage is crucial for consolidating language learning and improving future task performance. TBLT is highly effective in creating a dynamic and engaging classroom environment where students feel motivated to use English naturally and purposefully.

In some specialized schools, subjects like science and history are taught in English, enabling students to improve their language skills while gaining knowledge in other disciplines. CLIL represents a dual-focused approach where both content knowledge and language proficiency are developed simultaneously. This methodology allows students to use English as a medium of instruction in non-language subjects, fostering deeper engagement with the target language. For example, a science lesson might involve conducting experiments and reporting findings entirely in English, or a history lesson might include discussions and written essays in the target language. CLIL promotes

critical thinking, enhances cognitive development, and prepares students for academic and professional environments where English is the primary medium of communication. Moreover, it bridges the gap between language learning and subject knowledge, making English an essential tool for accessing information rather than just a subject to study. Teachers implementing CLIL must be skilled in both their subject area and English language instruction, requiring specialized training and resources. Despite its advantages, CLIL faces challenges such as limited teacher expertise and a lack of appropriate teaching materials, particularly in rural areas.

Despite the positive strides, several challenges persist. These include insufficient teacher training programs, lack of access to modern teaching resources in rural areas, and limited proficiency among some English teachers. Moreover, large class sizes and traditional assessment methods often hinder the effective implementation of innovative approaches.

To address these challenges, Uzbekistan plans to continue investing in teacher training programs, develop digital infrastructure, and create more opportunities for professional exchange programs. Collaboration with international educational organizations is expected to further strengthen the English language teaching sector.

Conclusion

The adoption of modern methods in teaching English in Uzbekistan reflects a significant shift towards learner-centered education and global integration. While challenges remain, ongoing reforms and increased investments provide a promising outlook for the future of English language education in the country.

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